

Contemporary research data and communication management - examples of good practice

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Introduction

Over the last decade, progress in digitalization has promoted many benefits for the research working environment and various facilitations for research data management. Notably, to take advantage of the new possibilities, researchers are facing diverse challenges. They have to align their established research workflows with the given dynamically changing digital transformations. Moreover, lately, the corona pandemic has represented a considerable need for flexible working arrangements and a driving force for remote-access-solutions. The following sections introduce good practice examples of the Aachener Verfahrenstechnik (AVT.CVT: Chair of Chemical Process Engineering) and the Institute of Applied Microbiology (iAMB); both institutes belong to the Rheinisch-Westfälisch-Technische Hochschule Aachen (RWTH). Here, concrete digital concepts for a) research data management according to good-scientific-practice¹, b) efficient team communication between the employees of the institutes, c) reliable remote-desktop connections as well as d) digital academic teaching have been developed already during the last years.

Good practice example I

The research projects within the AVT.CVT are focusing on the translation of fundamental scientific findings into sustainable processes which address global challenges. On the one hand, the researchers in the laboratories of the AVT.CVT are developing membrane types and materials for today's water supply or medical applications. On the other hand, processes to valorize CO₂ itself or to reduce CO₂ emissions in the fabrication of bulk chemicals are being

¹ https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/principles_dfg_funding/good_scientific_practice/

implemented and prepared for wide application. Various digital tools for facilitating internal and external communication, organizing data management of experimental research, and producing papers and proposals are being used by the institute members to manage researchers' work-life so far (see Figure 1). In the following sections, we will introduce a research data management tool and the communication platforms that are currently used at the institute.

Figure 1. Overview of the digital tools used for internal and external communication, experimental research, and scientific output (i.e., papers and proposals) in the AVT.CVT.

Research data management

The institute's leaders realized more than five years ago that the research data management in their laboratory required fundamental transformations. They agreed that the outcome of these transformations should fulfill the following criteria: a) The link between the raw data, processed data, metadata, and results to be published in peer-reviewed journals has to be concrete, precise and explicit. Researchers should save the data in a digital format; b) The availability of data should be guaranteed to facilitate sharing knowledge and collaboration within the institute and with external partners. Thus, knowledge loss due to fluctuating personnel should be avoided. c) Research data should be assessed via a remote-access tool to meet flexible working arrangements, irrespective of geographic distances. The kick-off for developing an own tool for data management was initiated by a former PhD student of the institute with excellent programming skills, who later commercialized his developments and founded the spin-off-company FURTHRresearch² in 2017. Their software FURTHRmind fulfills the criteria mentioned above (see Figure 2). The use of the software has been extended over the last years. Figure 3 shows that the acceptance among the researchers working in the laboratory has risen continuously. Therefore, the institute has increased the re-usability of research data and has avoided knowledge loss. For example, subsequent PhD students have continued working with the database and have addressed enhanced research questions without losing any time searching data and the corresponding metadata. Consequently,

² <https://www.furthr-research.com>

publications resulting from these subsequent research projects could be published straightforward and faster (see examples of three of those subsequent publications here³).

Figure 2. Overview of various ways of re-use of research data in the AVT.CVT (based on the use of the research data management software FURTHMind).

Figure 3 depicts the number of software users: while end of 2018 only 35 users were registered, mid of 2020 already 102 researchers and students have contributed and have managed data via FURTHMind on the server of the AVT.CVT. Correspondingly, the data storage size has increased: From the beginning of this year to the end of April, the data size rose by 140%. Due to the corona pandemic, arisen in 2020, the software prevents disruptions of the research workflow and the institute's output. Rotationally, researchers are continuously working in the laboratory, saving their measurements into the software and sharing their knowledge about their progress with their colleagues working in home-office. The software runs and is backed up on a server in the IT Center of the RWTH. It is accessible via a login-account (created by the local administrator) without the necessity of a VPN. The log-in process is double-encrypted and complies with the high data security standards of the RWTH. Researchers can invite internal as well as external (non-RWTH) partners to share their data. The software is programmed in Python and allows for modifications by the users. So far, the RWTH does not offer a specific agreement for licenses for FURTHMind; thus, the steering committee of the AVT.CVT has negotiated the financial details with the company.

³ Rall, D., Menne, D., Schweidtmann, A. M., Kamp, J., von Kolzenberg, L., Mitsos, A., & Wessling, M. (2019). Rational design of ion separation membranes. *Journal of Membrane Science*, 569, 209–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2018.10.013>; Rall, D., Schweidtmann, A. M., Aumeier, B. M., Kamp, J., Karwe, J., Ostendorf, K., ... Wessling, M. (2020). Simultaneous rational design of ion separation membranes and processes. *Journal of Membrane Science*, 600, 117860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2020.117860>; Kamp, J., Emonds, S., Wessling, M. (2020) Designing tubular composite membranes of polyelectrolyte multilayer on ceramic supports with nanofiltration and reverse osmosis transport properties. *Journal of Membrane Science*, Manuscript submitted.

Figure 3. The development of total numbers of users of the research data management software FURTHRmind and the respective total storage data size (GB) at the AVT.CVT during the last years.

Digital communication platforms

In addition to the implementation of FURTHRmind as a digital tool for research data management, multifunctional communication tools facilitating daily interaction between the institute members of the AVT.CVT were already implemented back in 2015. Currently, Mattermost⁴, a web-based open source⁵ messaging platform, is used. The introduction of this platform for team collaboration has enabled new forms of more flexible and autonomous work at the institute. Mattermost organizes conversations in teams and channels. The platform mainly provides one- on -one and group messaging, file as well as image and link sharing, and searchable message history. Figure 4 depicts the number of users and posts (messages) in April 2020. In the users' opinion, Mattermost offers a more transparent and traceable conversation history than conversations via Email. Moreover, researchers perceive conversations via Email as more time-consuming. The Mattermost-Team-Edition represents the basic open-source version, but the company sells additional features that are not included in the open-source edition (e.g., voice, video, and screen sharing, advanced user management, support, and administrative control). There are desktop clients for Windows, MacOS, and Linux and mobile apps for iOS and Android available. Mattermost provides details about security mechanisms on their homepage⁶.

There is currently an ongoing discussion about moving from Mattermost to the licensed alternative Microsoft® Teams⁷ communication platform. However, at the moment, only licenses of limited functionality are offered by the RWTH, but the institute members would

⁴ <https://mattermost.com>

⁵ MIT License for „Mattermost Team Edition“, Linux binary server compiled by Mattermost, Inc., AGPLv3 for uncompiled Mattermost server source code, Apache License 2.0 for admin tools and configuration files

⁶ <https://mattermost.com/security/>

⁷ https://www.microsoft.com/de-de/microsoft-365/microsoft-teams/group-chat-software?&ef_id=CjwKCAjwkun1BRAIEiwA2mJRWZ7XX0IbNUUcVr0_VfGkHVn7pU3PALzJ0AMtxZVpiTPruILEF-9dthoCTdsQAvD_BwE:G:s&OCID=AID2000957_SEM_CjwKCAjwkun1BRAIEiwA2mJRWZ7XX0IbNUUcVr0_VfGkHVn7pU

favor the extended version enabling extended communication and project management features. Microsoft® Teams describes their concept of IT security⁸ on their homepage.

Figure 4. Overview of the use of the messaging platform Mattermost (total active users, public channels, private channels and total posts) in the AVT.CVT during April 2020.

Good practice example II

The objective of research projects within the iAMB is to develop efficient universal pro- and eukaryotic cell factories using systems analysis, metabolic engineering, synthetic biology, and cultivation intensification. These platform organisms are able (depending on the integrated synthesis modules) to produce fuels or industrially relevant chemicals from renewable resources or alternative carbon sources like plastics waste. The iAMB laboratories comprise different safety areas of classes S1 and S2 to perform experiments in the areas of classical microbiology, analytical chemistry, biochemistry, and cell physiology in automated and semi-automated cultivation techniques.

Remote-desktop connection

The institute implemented multifunctional remote-control tools back in 2016 to provide a flexible working environment. Currently, the members use Anydesk⁹ as a reliable remote-desktop connection to enable access to various test benches that are actually located in the institute's safety zones. Thus, remote-control of the experimental methodologies is enabled, so all the safety precautions necessary when entering the laboratories can be omitted. In addition, Anydesk offers file management as well as team collaboration (e.g., whiteboard and chat features). The software is available for Windows, macOS, iOS, Android, Linux, FreeBSD, Raspberry Pi, Chrome OS and is at no charge for non-commercial use (see Figure 5). To protect from unauthorized access banking-standard TLS 1.2 technology and RSA 2048 asymmetric key exchange encryption is used to verify every connection (see more details about security issues at their homepage¹⁰). Postdocs and PhD-students are avocationally taking care of the software's functionality and are providing advice for their colleagues.

⁸ <https://www.microsoft.com/de-de/microsoft-365/microsoft-teams/security>

⁹ <https://anydesk.com/en>

¹⁰ <https://anydesk.com/en/features#fullListOfSecurity>

Figure 5. Screenshots of the user interface of Anydesk¹¹. For example, in case of the iAMB, the access to diverse test benches that are actually located in the institute’s safety zones are enabled in “sessions”.

Digital academic teaching

In digital academic teaching, the iAMB has positioned itself broadly to implement discussion and practical demonstration in the lectures of life science. Since 2017, several lectures, seminars, and trainings have been offered online by the lecturers. For example, the institute has conducted lectures such as “Introduction to Microbiology” and “General Genetics” and seminars as well as trainings such as “Physiology of Microorganisms” online.

The employees report that the digitalization of academic teaching poses a lot of advantages. For example, on the one hand, the students can learn at their own learning pace because the videos can be watched at any time (and can be repeated if necessary). Additionally, this suits students that do not have the same background knowledge as their fellow students because, e.g., they do not study biology. Moreover, due to a high number of students, practical experimental courses had to be offered twice per day for different groups of students before. Advantageously, the introductory seminars are offered online, which straightens the procedure and enables prerequisite learning independent of time and place. On the other hand, the lecturers agree that they can’t guarantee that the students are well prepared for the class. Furthermore, the interaction between students and the lecturer is reduced, so it is difficult to check if the learning material has been understood. Therefore, the iAMB uses online tools, including e-tests via Moodle¹² and a corresponding database comprising a collection of answers to the exercises. Moodle is a free and open-source learning management system enabling blended learning, distance education, flipped classroom and other e-learning projects. In addition, a glossary has been created, together with the students to increase the interaction during the learning processes.

Each lecturer of the institute has been responsible for his/her online seminar. The Centre for Teaching and Learning (Center für Lehr- und Lernservices, CLS)¹³ of the RWTH offers support in academic teaching. Furthermore, the Media-for-academic-teaching-team (Medien-für-die Lehre, MfL)¹⁴ of the RWTH Aachen supplies digital video and studio solutions for the lecturers. They provide full service in producing massive open online courses (MOOCs) that are composed of diverse modules of knowledge transfer and learning (e.g., videos and exercises).

¹¹ <https://anydesk.com/en/downloads/linux>, <https://anydesk.com/en/downloads/mac-os>

¹² <https://moodle.rwth-aachen.de>

¹³ <https://cls.rwth-aachen.de>

¹⁴ <https://www.medien.rwth-aachen.de>

Some RWTH-MOOCs can be audited for free, or students can choose to receive a verified certificate for a small fee¹⁵. Moreover, for self-editing of teaching material and videos the software by the lecturers of the iAMB, Camtasia¹⁶ turned out to be beneficial. The software is available for Mac OS and Windows and licenses are provided by the CLS (see details about security issues here¹⁷). Since 2020, Zoom¹⁸ has been introduced broadly for online teaching at the institute, and the platform is available for Mac OS, Windows, and mobile devices (additional product extensions can be bought¹⁹). A Zoom license (i.e., Zoom educational) has been available at the RWTH IT-services since the corona pandemic (see details about privacy and security here²⁰).

Conclusion and Outlook

The good practice examples above have demonstrated that there are various ways to increase digitalization in the academic domain. The introduced institutes have been clearly willing to address this issue and have carried out several digitalization projects focusing on research data management, digital team communication, remote-access-tools, and digital academic teaching during the last years. They have shown that digitalization in research encompasses a wide range of possibilities that have been based on the established components of the respective institutes. These have been used and expanded to increase the extent of digital potential. The efforts put in digitalization have turned out to be a return on investment for the AVT.CVT and the iAMB, at the latest with the beginning of the corona pandemic in 2020. However, as the advantages and benefits seem to prevail the disadvantages, the demand for modern digital solutions for a flexible research working environment will persist or even grow after the pandemic period, assuming that the increased and successful use of digital tools during this period has provoked a more widespread acceptance among the employees. However, ensuring privacy and security standards turned out to be a basic prerequisite for the extended usage of digital tools. Moreover, as employers contribute to their employees' mental as well as physical health, the people in charge have to be aware of possible misapplications of remote-access and digital communication access tools (e.g., tracking of employees).

Extending digitalization has implied a considerable challenge to the local administrators and other people in charge. They have been responsible for the implementation of digital technologies as well as for the service, support, and training of the users. In line with the extended use of digital tools, awareness about security issues (e.g., protection of data privacy, password management, protection against hacker attacks) had to be risen and the respective information had to be communicated amongst the employees. Importantly, all procedures had to be in accordance with the guidelines of the RWTH IT Center²¹. Consequently, the people in charge had to be involved in the reorganization of the institute's specific workflows. They had to be trained in some aspects of change management to provoke the new digital procedures. Regarding digital academic teaching, the lecturers had been confronted with technological as well as educational challenges. Notably, they had to restructure the content of their seminars and find digital solutions to meet the new requirements.

¹⁵ <https://www.edx.org/school/rwthx>

¹⁶ <https://www.techsmith.de/camtasia.html>

¹⁷ <https://www.techsmith.com/privacy.html>

¹⁸ <https://zoom.us>

¹⁹ <https://zoom.us/pricing>

²⁰ <https://zoom.us/docs/en-us/privacy-and-security.html>

²¹ <https://www.itc.rwth-aachen.de/cms/IT-Center/~ervt/IT-Center/?lidx=1>

Furthermore, establishing awareness about reliable research data management according to good scientific practice has led to new fields of activity and even to new vocational positions: Data Stewards, employed at e.g., clusters of excellence at the RWTH, are providing advice and helping to develop appropriate solutions for research data management and sharing.²² Thus, they are assuring that data management activities are performed to best practice levels and meet the expectations and requirements of funding agencies. Additionally, the research data management team at the RWTH²³ offers general support and training concerning research data management. Finally, to put the findings of the good practice examples discussed above in a nutshell, combining the advantages of sound research data management and modern digital technologies for academic communication and teaching seems to be a major driver for innovation and future competitiveness.

²² Data Stewards an der RWTH Aachen University – Aufbau eines flexiblen Netzwerks; D. Hausen, J. Rosenberg, U. Trautwein-Bruns, A. Schwarz; Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement, submitted, 2020.

²³ <https://www.rwth-aachen.de/cms/root/Forschung/~Inaw/Forschungsdatenmanagement/?lidx=1>